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GDP Impacts of Trans Mountain Oil Pipeline Crown Corporation in Canada

Bell, Peter

16 December 0020

Online at <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/127363/>

MPRA Paper No. 127363, posted

Abstract

This article uses the financial statements for the crown corporation called Trans Mountain Corp to model the GDP impacts of an oil pipeline mega-project. In 2018, the Government of Canada paid approximately \$4.5 billion to Kinder Morgan to acquire the project and create the Trans Mountain Corp crown corporation. The government paid \$28 billion in capital costs, making total costs greater than \$32 billion for the pre-production phase 2018-2025. The project recently started production with around \$2-3 billion in revenue per year, which is expected to continue for more than 20 years. This paper builds a toy model of the project and shows that the project's NPV in 2018 was negative \$11 billion at a 10% discount rate, whereas it is over \$20 billion in 2025. The paper also estimates the GDP impacts of this government spending during the pre-production and production phase, and estimates a GDP multiplier as if the Canadian military funded the project entirely.

Keywords: GDP, Canada, Pipeline, Keystone XL, Kinder Morgan, Energy, Oil

JEL Codes:

B5 - Current Heterodox Approaches

C60 - General

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Modeling

C8 - Data Collection and Data Estimation

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H54 - Infrastructures Other Public Investment and
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K2 - Regulation and Business Law

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L3 - Nonprofit Organizations and Public Enterprise

L32 - Public Enterprises ; Public-Private Enterprises

L5 - Regulation and Industrial Policy

L7 - Industry Studies: Primary Products and
Construction

L72 - Mining, Extraction, and Refining: Other

Nonrenewable Resources

N5 - Agriculture, Natural Resources, Environment, and
Extractive Industries

O1 - Economic Development

O13 - Agriculture ; Natural Resources ; Energy ;
Environment ; Other Primary Products

O2 - Development Planning and Policy

P1 - Capitalist Systems

Q3 - Nonrenewable Resources and Conservation

Q32 - Exhaustible Resources and Economic

Development

Q33 - Resource Booms

Q5 - Environmental Economics

Y1 - Data: Tables and Charts

GDP from Mining in Canada and A New Mega Project

This article uses the financial statements for the crown corporation called Trans Mountain Corp to model the GDP impacts of an oil pipeline mega-project. In 2018, the Government of Canada paid approximately \$4.5 billion to Kinder Morgan to acquire the project and create the Trans Mountain Corp crown corporation. The government paid \$28 billion in capital costs, making total costs greater than \$32 billion for the pre-production phase 2018-2025. The project recently started production with around \$2-3 billion in revenue per year, which is expected to continue for more than 20 years. This paper builds a toy model of the project and shows that the project's NPV in 2018 was negative \$11 billion at a 10% discount rate, whereas it is over \$20 billion in 2025. The paper also estimates the GDP impacts of this government spending during the pre-production and production phase, and estimates a GDP multiplier as if the Canadian military funded the project entirely.

Cash Flow Model of Pipeline Mega Project

The Government of Canada (2025a) writes, *“The Government of Canada acquired TMX from Kinder Morgan in 2018. This was a serious and necessary investment made in the national interest... The federal government does not intend to be the long-term owner of the project, and it will launch a divestment process in due course.”* This statement includes a few markers for government policy, such as the plan to divest the project in the future. What valuation will the project sell at, and what kind of return will the government earn from their divestment versus its investment? What kind of GDP impacts will the project have before it is divested? There are many ways to explore these questions, and this paper presents a basic approach that starts by building a model of the project cash flows.

The Trans Mountain Corp. summary of quarterly results (2025a) provides the following information on costs: *“Since the inception of the project, \$28.6 billion in construction capital spending has been incurred, plus \$5.1 billion in financial carrying costs have been capitalized. The TMEP was mechanically complete, with the final “golden weld” occurring on April 11, 2024. The commercial commencement date for the Expanded System was May 1, 2024.”* All figures are Canadian dollars.

The 2025 run rate for revenue is \$2-3 billion, with operating costs around \$0.5 billion. It is unclear what the “sustaining” capital costs will be going forward, but the total accrued capital costs from 2018 to 2025 were over \$28 billion, as noted above. The project started in 2018 with \$28.6 billion in construction capital spending for the total 2018-2025, approximately \$4 billion in capital spending per year. Chart 1 shows how revenue increased dramatically after the project came online in the 2024-Q3 quarterly report.

Chart 1: Quarterly Cashflow for TMX Project Since Start of Production

The Trans Mountain Corp (2025a) Note 2 in the Financial Statements shows that revenue is expected to average \$2-3 billion per year going forward indefinitely. *“The contractually committed revenue primarily consists of customer contracts for firm service, which have minimum volume commitment payment obligations. The actual revenue recognized on these customer contracts can vary... generally limited to the minimum revenue commitment under these customer contracts... Contractually committed revenues associated with the 15 and 20-year committed contracts for transportation service that total approximately 80% of the capacity...”* The actual revenue could be higher than the assumption of \$2-3 billion per year.

The financial performance of an oil pipeline business has several distinct features. For example, the business has long-term contracts where the pipeline is guaranteed to get paid minimum amounts over time. For another, the operating costs are also a relatively small proportion of revenues, whereas the capital costs are relatively high.

It is expensive to build new pipelines; after the pipeline is built, it yields reliable financial performance. The reason for the relatively low risk profile of the pipeline industry reflects the way risk sharing happens in the oil business and how governments regulate pipelines to avoid disasters in terms of financial or operational failure. In contrast, the oil companies using the pipeline take on the risk of uncertain oil prices. Transaction cost economics provides a framework further to analyze these features beyond the scope of this article.

Chart 2: Toy Model of Net Cash Flow at Trans Mountain Corp

Chart 2 shows the net cash flow for the project each year. For the pre-production phase 2018-2025, there are no revenues, but there are acquisition costs and capital costs. For the production phase 2025-2045 and beyond, there are revenues and operating costs. The total life of

the project is uncertain and could be more than 20 years. The total revenues are uncertain and could grow at compounding rates over time beyond the baseline revenue assumptions from Trans Mountain Corp (2025a).

The cash flow in Chart 2 focuses on total revenue, not net income. Total revenue represents an increase in total economic activity, which is a focus for the government that is motivated by national interest, not profitability. Also, there is potential for the difference between revenue and income to be offset by growth in revenue because current revenue is based on 80% of total capacity. It is essential to be clear about who is paying for what costs and capturing what revenue in this model of a crown corporation building a mega project.

Charts 3 and 4 below show the sensitivity of NPV for the cash flow to different discount rates. In 2018, the project NPV includes the initial acquisition cost of \$4 billion in 2018, capital costs of \$4 billion each year from 2018 to 2025, and revenues of \$2 billion per year for 2025-2045 as in Chart 2.

Chart 3 shows that the project value was generally negative in 2018 when the government acquired it. At a 10% discount rate, the total project value was negative \$20 billion in 2018, which is one reason why the industry sold it at the time. Large capital spending requirements and negative NPV were significant impediments to development, which meant there was no incentive for a profit-motivated business to advance the project. However, the government chose to buy and advance the project because its motivation is the broader national interest. Can we quantify that broader interest and the impact of the project?

It is interesting to note the price the government paid of \$4.5 billion compared with the project NPV at the time -\$20 billion from Chart 3. Did the government over-pay relative to project economics at the time? Why would the government do that? What was the basis for \$4.5 billion acquisition costs, total accumulated spending by Kinder Morgan to 2018 or something else? These questions are beyond the scope of this article, but they show several interesting ways to extend the analysis in this article.

Chart 3: Comparison of Discount Rates for NPV in 2018

Sensitivity Analysis for Economic Model 2018-20245

Chart 4: Comparison of Discount Rates for NPV at 2025

Sensitivity Analysis for Economic Model 2025-2045

Chart 4 shows that the project valuation was positive in 2025 after it had already been built. The NPV calculation at 2025 assumes all capital costs are already paid, and the NPV is based on future cash flows from 2025 to 2045. In 2018, project valuation was based on acquisition costs, capital costs, operating costs, and revenue estimated from 2018 to 2045; in 2025, project valuation was based on revenue and operating costs from 2025 to 2045.

Chart 4 shows that the project has a positive NPV of around \$10-15 billion in 2025. In 2018, Kinder Morgan sold the entire project for less than \$5 billion when the project's NPV was -\$20 billion. Currently, the project NPV is around \$10-15 billion. The NPV has increased by \$30-35 billion from 2018 to 2025. For comparison, the acquisition costs were \$4.5 billion in 2018, and capital costs \$28 billion from 2018 to 2025; the total government spending is around \$32 billion for the same timeline. The project valuation has increased by a similar amount as the total investment by the government from 2018 to 2025: \$32 billion. Starting with the \$4.5 billion acquisition costs (excluding capital costs), this represents an annual growth rate of 36% for project valuation.

Chart 5 below is based on the NPV Profile method from Bell (2017). The project shows a “rising” NPV profile where value increases as capital costs are incurred and the project advances towards production from 2018 to 2025. After 2025, the NPV profile is flat because of the assumption that it is a steady-state business with an ongoing annual cash flow \$2 billion per year. At a 10% discount rate, \$2 billion per year has an NPV \$20 billion, ten times larger. This model assumes the project earns the same revenues in perpetuity, but the real amounts may be much larger and growing over time.

Chart 6 shows all aspects of the basic economic model. All costs include acquisition, capital, and operating costs. One type of revenue. Note that the NPV Profile reach a maximum in 2025 when capital costs stop, and revenues start.

Chart 5: Project Valuation at Different Times using NPV Profile

NPV Profile for Economic Model 2018-2045 (10% Discount)

Chart 6: Comparison of Revenues, Costs, and NPV Profile

Economic model 2018-20245

Military Funding of the Pipeline Mega Project

Consider a scénario where the Canadian military funds the entire project itself. It is unclear which branch of the military would fund the project, but the broad definition of military spending within NATO provides opportunities for Canada to use military spending to benefit domestic infrastructure. There are several ways to measure the GDP impacts of this scénario, and I assume the military pays for all project costs and earns all project revenues. I also assume that the military only uses materials and personnel from Canada, so all project spending has a multiplier effect on GDP in Canada.

I start by looking backwards to the 2018-2025 pre-production phase. The GDP multiplier from capital spending is unknown, but it is greater than 1x. When the military spends on capital costs for the project, that amount directly increases GDP. When the military pays Canadian companies to provide the capital items, I assume the Canadian companies spend that same money again in Canada the same year as an indirect increase for GDP. Together, the total GDP multiplier is 2x in this scénario. It is beyond the scope of this article to explore how capital costs generally have long-term effects, so the capital costs may actually have an accumulated or compounding effect on GDP for several years in addition to a same-year effect. I assume the military pays for the acquisition costs \$4 billion to Kinder Morgan, but there is no GDP impact because it is a foreign company.

The project has \$4 billion in capital costs each year, and with a 2x multiplier on capital costs, the total GDP impact is \$8 billion per year during the pre-production phase. Over the entire seven-year period 2018-2025, the project has a total GDP impact of \$56 billion at a 2x multiplier and a direct cost to the military of \$32 billion. For comparison, total military spending is approximately \$40 billion per year and must increase to \$60 billion to reach NATO targets (Government of Canada, 2025b). This project could represent approximately \$5 billion per year in new spending for the Canadian military during the pre-production phase, which is a relatively large amount at approximately 25% of the target increase in overall military spending.

To calculate the GDP multiplier for the project going forward during the production phase 2025-2045, I assume the Canadian military pays all the operating costs and earns all the revenues. I assume the military only pays companies in Canada for operating costs, and those companies then spend all that money again in the same year, so that operating costs have a 2x multiplier on GDP. Annual operating costs are \$0.5 billion for 20 years, which means the total military spending is \$10 billion towards operating costs and \$20 billion GDP impacts during production from 2025 to 2045. This total amount of military spending of \$0.5 billion per year on operating costs represents a relatively small amount compared to the total military budgets.

There are additional impacts from the project during production since the revenue represents a new amount of the primary value of natural resources production in Canada. I assume all of the revenue gets spent again in the same year within Canada, so it is a 2x multiplier for total GDP impact caused by project revenue. The total revenue is \$2-3 billion per year, so the GDP impact is \$4-6 billion per year from 2025 to 2045. The average of \$5 billion per year for 20 years is a total \$100 billion GDP impact for the project going forward, which would represent a relatively large amount of GDP overall and the largest single new source of revenue for the Canadian military.

The total direct cost to the government during the production phase from 2025 to 2045, as total military spending on operating costs is equal to \$10 billion, which causes a \$120 billion total impact on GDP. This is calculated as \$100 billion GDP impact from project revenue and \$20 billion GDP impact from operating costs. Total military spending is \$10 billion, versus GDP impacts \$120 billion, which means the GDP multiplier is 12x during the production phase for the project. This large multiplier in 2025 reflects the accumulated capital costs of projects and economies of pipeline business. In contrast, the multiplier on military spending on GDP impact was only 2x during the pre-production phase; total military spending on capital costs is \$28 billion from 2018 to 2025, which creates a \$56 billion GDP impact over the same timeline.

During the pre-production phase, the project had more than \$50 billion in GDP impacts over 7 years. During the production phase, the project had \$120 billion in GDP impacts over 20

years. The overall average annual GDP impact is \$5-10 billion from 2018 to 2045. The average military spending from 2018 to 2045 is approximately \$2 billion (acquisition costs plus capital costs plus operating costs \$55 billion over 27 years). The relatively significant impact on Canadian GDP relative to costs reflects how this mega project was deemed to be in the national interest in 2018, even though it had a negative NPV at the time.

The project revenues are \$2-3 billion per year for 20 years, 2025-2045, with operating costs of \$0.5 billion for +75% operating margin. The total project costs before 2025 are \$32 billion (acquisition and capital costs) versus operating income of \$2 billion, which means the project has a 15-year payback period. Mega projects typically have a long payback period and a longer potential useful life. The current NPV of \$20 billion is actually less than the total cost base of \$32 billion. In terms of a valuation based on profitability, the project now has reliable revenue and relatively small costs. However, based on the national interest, the project has a significant multiplier effect on GDP. It is possible to extend this analysis further to consider effects upstream on oil producers who use the pipeline that otherwise couldn't transport this material to global markets. It is also possible to estimate taxes generated by increased GDP to compare with government funding costs for the project.

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